

Students' Work Experience Programme: Terrazzo Flooring And Moulding Of Interlocking Tiles

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ABSTRACT

Theoretical knowledge alone would not usually prepare an educated person for the world of work. A productive individual must not only be knowledgeable in theory but must also be versatile in the application of skills to perform defined jobs or work, hence the need for Students' Work Experience Program (SWEP). The 2012/ 2013 Students' Work Experience Programme (SWEP) was undertaken at Afe Babalola University, Ado Ekiti, Nigeria (ABUAD) by all 200 and 300 Level engineering students. The Students' Work Experience Programme (SWEP) helps develop in the students, a logical mode of thinking and reasoning that promotes a practical application of acquired theoretical, knowledge in overcoming technical and professional challenges. Besides it also helps in training the students on how to acknowledge and appreciate the numerous professional challenges of their immediate environment and the society at large and offer solutions, which their knowledge empowerment avails them. The SWEP featured activities in three key Engineering fields namely: Mechanical, Electrical and Civil. The Civil Project include: moulding of interlocking tiles, terrazzo floor making, participation in on-going construction works on campus, sewage system etc. During the SWEP, students were resourcefully engaged in terrazzo flooring and moulding of interlocking tiles as well as other various engineering activities within the school. These make students conversant with laboratory, workshop tools and machineries and to practicalise what they have been taught theoretically thereby acquainting them with workshop and industrial practices.

Keywords: Interlocking tiles, Moulding, Terrazzo, Sewage System.

INTRODUCTION

The Students' Work Experience Programme (SWEP) helps in developing the students' innovative, creative abilities and skills relevant to their programme. It engages students in workshop and outdoor manual labour so that they can appreciate the dignity of labour. This aspect of training is part of the NUC approved programme for engineering students to produce competent Engineers and professionals of excellence in the future. SWEP was designed not only to expose the students to skills acquisition but also inculcate in them the development of right team spirit as well as expose them to rudimentary expectations for the world of work. The major background behind the embankment of students in SWEP was to expose them to the industrial environment and enable them develop occupational competencies so that they can readily contribute their quota to national economic and technological.

Interlocking tile is a type of floor finishing and unlike plain tiles, are designed so that their edges fit mechanically with one another, to provide a weather seal, and usually used in flooring outside the house. Interlocking Tiles are known for their immaculate finesse, designs and strength. These are made of fine quality stone and can withstand toughest daily grind [1]. Anti-fungal and non-skid and have longer life these are few features for which these are highly appreciated. These tiles are available at very nominal prices and can be availed in the designs and in customized specifications as per clients' needs and demands.

The modern interlocking floor tile is a flat, smooth, single lap interlocking design with a slate like appearance enhanced by a broken bond laying pattern. In the moulding of an interlocking floor tiles there are some mixing ratios that are used.

Mixing Ratio

Mixing ratio is the portion of one aggregate to the other. Chaos is also another name that is used in replacing mixture of cements, sands and water. The ratio of mixture used in the moulding of an interlocking floor tiles are:

1. 1:3- this is the ratio of one (1) head pan of cement to the ratio of three (3) head pan of stone dust.
2. 1:6- this is the ratio of one (1) bag of cement to the ratio of six (6) head pan of stone dust.

Curing Process of Interlocking Tiles:

This is the process of controlling the extent moisture of the interlocking floor tile when drying. This is also the process of wetting the interlocking floor tiles to avoid cracking and help to get the maximum strength of the tiles. Curing is the process of controlling the rate and extent of moisture loss from concrete during cement hydration [2]. It may be either after it has been placed in position (or during the manufacture of concrete products), thereby providing time for the hydration of the cement to occur. Since the hydration of cement does take time – days, and even weeks rather than hours – curing must be undertaken for a reasonable period of time if the concrete is to achieve its potential strength and durability. Curing may also encompass the control of

temperature since this affects the rate at which cement hydrate [3]. Concrete that is allowed to dry out quickly also undergoes considerable early age drying shrinkage. Inadequate or insufficient curing is one of main factors contributing to weak, powdery surfaces with low abrasion resistance.

Concrete can be kept moist (and in some cases at a favourable temperature) by three curing methods:

1. Methods that maintain the presence of mixing watering the concrete during the early hardening period. These include ponding or immersion, spraying or fogging, and saturated wet coverings. These methods afford some cooling through evaporation, which is beneficial in hot weather [4] [5].

2. Methods that reduce the loss of mixing water from the surface of the concrete. This can be done by covering the concrete with impervious paper or plastic sheets, or by applying membrane-forming curing compounds

3. Methods that accelerate strength gain by supplying heat and additional moisture to the concrete. This is usually accomplished with live steam, heating coils, or electrically heated forms or pads.

Effect of duration of curing on properties of concrete

The strength of concrete is affected by a number of factors, one of which is the length of time for which it is kept moist [6]

Importance of Curing on Interlocking Floor Tiles

1. To get the maximum strength of the interlocking floor tiles
2. To avoid cracks on the interlocking floor tiles.

The maximum strength of the interlocked tiles is given as:

$$\text{Maximum strength} = \frac{\text{Load at fracture (KN)}}{\text{Area of specimen (mm}^2\text{)}} \quad (2.1)$$

$$\text{Area of specimen} = \text{length} \times \text{breadth} \quad (2.2)$$

Terrazzo

Terrazzo is a composite material, poured in place or precast, which is used for floor and wall treatments. It consists of marble, quartz, granite, glass, or other suitable chips, sprinkled and poured with a binder that is cementitious, chemical, or a combination of both. Terrazzo is cured and then ground and polished to a smooth surface or otherwise finished to produce a uniformly textured surface. Terrazzo is the composite product of marble chippings (the chippings used are mostly in an average of half an inch) and other durable aggregates poured and pre-casted. The cement used here could be of any colour.

There are two types of casting which are the insitu casting and the pre-cast [7]. The insitu casting is a type of casting that is made where it is needed while the pre-cast is made in one place then taken to the place where it is needed for use. The pre-cast is used in a place like the staircase because it is not going to be easy for machine to be carried from one point to another just to wash the terrazzo, so the pre-cast is made and washed in a place before taken to another place where it is needed. When making such terrazzo, the terrazzo has to be soaked in water for about twenty to thirty minutes or else it may break when laying it, this is because water serves to bind the terrazzo to the floor. When laying the terrazzo, there may be space, this space is blocked or reduced using the white cement or else, the terrazzo might remove from the wall and this might even lead to damage.

Terrazzo could be done on the wall but it would be more expensive because pre-cast would be used to make the terrazzo first before putting it on the wall [8].

Advantages of Terrazzo Floor over other materials

1. It is extremely hard wearing that it could outlive almost other types of hard floorings. Therefore, using this material also ensures low and effective cost.

2. If hygiene and health reasons are to be considered, terrazzo is highly favoured because it is easy to clean and maintain.

3. The material has no organic solvent components, thus there will be no fear of inhaling toxic vapours or exposures to harmful chemicals when these are installed in floors

4. It has also higher slip resistance compared to other flooring materials e.g. tiled floor and among the many factors considered in choosing materials for architectural use, beauty is never missing.

5. Terrazzo is either used in indoor or outdoor parts of the buildings has a wide range of colours, designs, and shapes; from bright, to bold, to classic architectural styles.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The following materials and tools were used while moulding the interlocking tiles:

- ❖ Head pan
- ❖ Trowel
- ❖ Mould
- ❖ Spade
- ❖ Shovel
- ❖ Cement
- ❖ stone dust

The following materials and tools were employed while making the terrazzo tiles:

- ❖ Marble
- ❖ Ebonite strike
- ❖ Cement
- ❖ Terrazzo washing machine
- ❖ Sieved sand such as plaster sand
- ❖ Roller machine
- ❖ Schist material etc

The following are the materials; tools and equipment used for moulding of interlocking tiles and terrazzo flooring

Fig. 1: Marble

Fig. 2: Terrazzo Washing Machine

Fig. 3: Ebonite Strike (Black line)

Fig. 4: Schist Material

Fig. 5: Head Pan

Fig. 6: Shovel

Moulding of Interlocking Tile

The following procedure are followed in the process of making an interlocking tiles

Washing of moulds: Washing of moulds is necessary because, cement based on its nature, if mixed with impurities would lead to loss of strength and as a matter of fact. During the purpose of this exercise, the washing of moulds was done making use of sponge and water.

Fig. 7: Washing of Moulds

(1) **Lubricating:** This is the next stage after washing the moulds; moulds are to be lubricated to reduce friction effect [9]. If not well lubricated, face of tile binds with the mould which

may lead to rough tile surface and even breakage or crack when removing the tile from the mould. The students made use of diesel in lubricating the moulds but any other lubricating fluid can be used.

Fig. 8: Lubricated Moulds

Measuring of aggregates: This is the stage at which we measure the concrete mixture. Different sand such as granite can be used, but we are made to know that the university is making use of stone dust due to its igneous nature. The ratio of stone dust to cement is ratio 6:1 respectively, one can as well say 3 full head pan of stone dust to half bag of cement or full head pan of cement, since two full head pan of cement makes a bag of cement.

Fig. 9: Measured Aggregates

Fig. 10: Mixing of Aggregates

(2) **Moulding:** the mixed concrete is then poured inside the moulds to bring out the shape of the interlocking tiles.

Fig. 11: Moulding Process

Fig. 12: Sandcretres in Moulds

Curing: Interlocking tiles are cured by moistening it with water so as for it to increase in strength and also curing also aid in avoidance of cracks [10]. It is better to cure every day after which the interlocking tile will assume its maximum strength within 28 days. The interlocking tile attain 16% strength in a day, 40% in three days until which it attain it maximum strength which is 99% on the twenty eight days.

Fig. 13: Interlocked Tiles near Completion

Terrazzo Flooring

In making terrazzo, the first thing needed is to screed followed by dividing the area to the required size and pattern. A rubber called ebonite strike is used to divide the floor into different shapes. After this is done, water is deliberately poured on the floor, so has to serve as a binder between the existing floor and the material. It must be noted that surface color depends on the color of cement used in mixing the aggregates. The chippings casted inside the already segmented area also contain the schist and marble mixed with sieved sand such as plaster sand. After this mixture is already in place, the chippings is poured in a regular pattern inside the segmented area, a roller machine is used to compact it together. After that, one allows it to set then one wash it with the terrazzo washing machine. This machine has a compartment underneath that housed the terrazzo washing stone which grinds and smoothening the surface of the casted aggregates/chippings, in which water is used to wash the slurries produced during this process. This is followed by washing with broom again before the second washing called polishing also using the terrazzo washing and allowed to dry. In a case whereby the floor is polished and there are other works such as electrical or plumbing work etc going on in the site, sawdust may be sprinkled on the terrazzo so to avoid foreign materials such as dirt been introduced to it and after the completion of this work, the sawdust is swept and thus the terrazzo is ready.

Fig. 14: Terrazzo Washing Machine Grinding and Smoothening Chippings

Fig. 15: Washed and Polished Terrazzo Floor

EXPERIENCE GAINED

Exposure to Civil Engineering practices: terrazzo floor making, mixing of aggregates, moulding of interlocking tiles etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Required shapes and nature of interlocking tiles were obtained at an appropriate maximum strength by curing which also lock in moisture

Table 1: percentage strength obtained after casting

Days after casting	% strength obtained
1	16%
3	40%
7	55%
14	60%
21	95%
28	99%

The 28th day is the maximum day before crushing (to determine the maximum strength of the interlocking tiles) with the compression machine.

After successful completion

Fig. 16: Finished Interlocked Tile

Fig. 17: Moulded Interlocking Tiles

Fig. 18: Terrazzo Floor

CONCLUSION

After the successful completion of the SWEP, the following conclusions were drawn:

- ❖ The programme makes students conversant with laboratory, workshop tools and machineries and to practicalise what they have been taught theoretically.
- ❖ (ii) It enables students to obtain employment experience in preparation for future entry into various organizations
- ❖ (iii) The feasibility of the program helps to gather more knowledge and experience on workshop and industrial practises.
- ❖ (iv) It also enables students to be proficient, resourceful, dynamic, creative, efficient, proactive and versatile in the application of acquired skill to solve engineering challenges.

RECOMMENDATIONS

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- ❖ Curriculum revision: Tertiary Institution should revise their curricula and introduce new courses to meet the needs of employers in the public and private sectors. Courses that will also improve self-reliability and make them employers of labour should also be introduced.
- ❖ Increased Supervision from School and regulatory bodies.
- ❖ Strong synergy between academic, industrial and research institutions.
- ❖ Adequate sensitization of students through periodic seminars and workshops.
- ❖ Formulation of good policies to guide the running of the scheme nationally and enhance the scheme.

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